

A survey on Birds & Nature

2022 Summer - Camp FRESH!

Anita Purves Nature Center

The University of Illinois and the Urbana Park District is partnering to learn more about your experiences with birds and nature! Your information will be kept confidential, and you can choose not to participate in this study. Please answer each question carefully. Thank you!

Name: _____

Date: _____

Section 1. Please share what you know and think about birds.

1. What are the **defining characteristics** of a bird?

2. What **species** of birds can you identify?

3. How do you **feel** about birds?

4. How can we help **protect** birds?

Section 2. These questions are about how you feel and think about birds. There are no right or wrong answers. Please check (✓) a box below a face that shows how much you like each activity!

I like to... (↓)						
	Don't like it at all.	Not really.	OK.	Like it.	Love it!	Don't know.
1. See birds in nature.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Touch birds.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Love and care for birds.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Learn more about birds.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Think about birds.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Listen to bird songs.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7. Live close to birds.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
8. Be in the outdoors where birds are around.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section 3. We want to know how much you feel you are part of nature. There are no right or wrong answers. Please check (✓) one of the pictures below that shows how close you are to nature.

1.			
4.			

Section 4. We want to know how important nature and the environment are to you. Please check (✓) a box below a face that shows the importance of each item to you!

Is this (↓) important to you?						
	Not at all.	Meh.	Little bit.	Yes.	Very much!	Don't know.
1. Respecting the earth	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Getting along with other animals and plants	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Being part of nature	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Protecting nature	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Not polluting nature	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Section 5. We want to know how much you learned about birds through our program. Please check (✓) a box below a face that shows how you responded to the bird activities!

	Not at all!	Meh.	Little bit.	Yes.	Very much!	Don't know.
1. I talked about the bird activities with friends, family, or other people I know.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. I thought about what other kids and camp leaders did and said during the bird activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. I actively participated in the bird activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. I would like to participate in other bird activities in the future.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for sharing your answers!
 If you have questions about the survey or the research project,
 please talk to [author].
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